

The Oxidizing Action of Alkaline Ferricyanide and the Composition of Higher Oxides of Cobalt.

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Potassium ferricyanide in alkaline solution has been used extensively as an oxidizing agent and its use has led to the development of many important analytical methods. The present work was undertaken in order to investigate its oxidizing action upon cobalt and nickel salts, the constitution of their higher oxides, and the possibility of establishing a rapid volumetric method for their estimation.

A number of higher oxides of cobalt have been described, *viz.*, Co_2O_3 , Co_3O_5 , Co_3O_7 , Co_4O_9 , Co_5O_{11} , Co_6O_{13} , Co_7O_{15} , Co_8O_{17} , and CoO_2 . It is extremely doubtful whether all of them have separate existence: most of them are simply mixtures of two or more definite oxides. It is also quite possible that different oxidizing agents behave differently towards solutions of cobalt and nickel salts leading to products of different compositions. Lately however Howell has thoroughly studied the constitution of the higher oxides of cobalt (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 65) and of nickel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 669; 1772) obtained by the action of alkaline hypochlorite solutions. In the case of cobalt the only definite oxide obtained by him was Co_2O_3 . In the case of nickel the oxide, Ni_2O_3 and an unstable peroxide, NiO_2 were obtained. The action of alkaline ferricyanide upon cobalt salts, which forms the

subject of the present paper, indicates, however, the existence of Co_3O_4 and Co_2O_3 as definite oxides and a higher one of the peroxide type. Nickel, on the other hand, was found to be very little affected by alkaline ferricyanide showing that it is much less easily oxidized than cobalt.

The oxidizing action of potassium ferricyanide depends upon the fact that, in alkaline solution in the presence of an oxidizable substance, it is reduced to ferrocyanide. Kassner (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1896, 235, 330) studied the behaviour of the ferricyanides as oxidizing agents, the nature of the oxidation and the conditions under which they can be used to best advantage. He found that potassium ferricyanide solution when mixed with potassium hydroxide solution, was stable in the dark at low temperatures only; when heated to above 60° or exposed to direct sunlight, it was partially decomposed, ferric hydroxide was deposited and the solution contained ammonia and cyanide. When alkali carbonate was substituted for the hydroxide the extent of the decomposition was considerably less and was reduced still further when an alkali bicarbonate was employed. According to him a permanent ferricyanide solution bath for oxidizing and bleaching purposes can be maintained in the dark at a temperature below 60° . But the decomposition of the reagent itself under the conditions of experiments described in this paper has been shown to be negligibly small and not seriously to affect the results of a quantitative study of the reactions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Stability of Alkaline Ferricyanide Solution.

Three small beakers were taken. The first contained a strongly alkaline solution of potassium ferricyanide;

the second, the same solution in contact with a filter paper; the third, an alkaline solution of potassium ferrocyanide. All were left exposed to the air and, after 45 minutes, portions from each of them were tested. No ferrocyanide was detected in the first solution; only a green colouration with acidified ferric-alum solution was obtained in the second solution and the third gave no test for ferricyanide. This proves that alkaline ferricyanide solution alone in the absence of direct sunlight is fairly stable to air and if any change takes place at all it must be very slow. In the presence of organic matter like filter paper a slight decomposition occurs which can also be neglected for all practical purposes in such rapid analytical operations as were followed in the present investigation.

Procedure.

An alkali solution was prepared and the strength was daily determined with a standard acid solution. A solution of $N/20 \cdot \text{KMnO}_4$ was prepared and its strength was determined against chemically pure potassium ferrocyanide. Crystals of "Merck's Reagent" potassium ferricyanide were washed and dissolved in water. The solution was made up to a definite volume and its strength determined daily against the permanganate solution. A solution of "Merck's Reagent" potassium hydroxide was made and the amount of KOH and K_2CO_3 per c.c. of the solution was determined daily.

Two series of experiments were performed. In the first, the amount of alkali was kept constant while the amount of ferricyanide was progressively increased; in the second, the alkali was gradually increased while the amount of ferricyanide was kept constant. In the first series the amount of alkali employed was in excess of that required for the precipitation of all the cobalt as cobalt

hydroxide and for the complete oxidation of the latter to the CoO_2 stage. In the second series, the amount of ferricyanide used was in excess of that necessary for the complete oxidation of all the cobalt to the CoO_2 stage. The estimations were then carried out in the following manner. A definite volume of chemically pure nickel-free cobalt nitrate solution containing a known amount of cobalt was run into a beaker from a burette and made up to 50 c.c. with water. Standard ferricyanide solution was run from a burette into a measuring cylinder containing the required amount of alkali previously introduced into it from another burette and made up to 100 c.c. with water. This was then slowly added to the cobalt solution with continuous stirring. The cylinder was washed with another 100 c.c. of water and the latter was added to the cobalt solution thus making the total volume up to 250 c.c. The mixture was then thoroughly stirred with a mechanical stirrer for about half an hour and transferred to a 500 c.c. measuring flask, the beaker was well washed, and the washings also added to the liquid in the flask. Water was then added up to the mark and the flask thoroughly shaken. The solution was filtered through a dry filter paper; first 20—25 c.c. of the filtrate were rejected and then 100 c.c. of the filtrate were acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and titrated with KMnO_4 solution. Table I gives the results of the first series of experiments. These results have been plotted on a curve in Fig. I. The equivalent amounts on the graph are calculated on the basis of the amount of cobalt taken as unit equivalent. Thus one equivalent of available oxygen is the amount necessary for the conversion to Co_2O_3 of all the cobaltous oxide corresponding with the amount of the cobalt salt taken. The equivalents of alkali and ferricyanide have also been represented on the same basis. In the case of the alkali, however, a necessary deduction has

Fig. I

been made for the precipitation of the cobalt as hydroxide from the solution of its salt.

TABLE I.
Cobalt taken = 0.09 gm.

KOH	K ₂ CO ₃	Total alkali.	Potassium ferri-cyanide.	Equivalents of available oxygen.
0.7376 g.	0.0199 g.	0.7575 g.	0.15 g. = 0.2986 eqv.	0.2852
0.7376	0.0257	0.7624	0.20 = 0.3981 "	0.3820
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	0.26 = 0.5175 "	0.5100
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	0.335 = 0.6670 "	0.6690
0.7387	0.0153	0.7540	0.38 = 0.7564 "	0.6690
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	0.45 = 0.8958 "	0.8920
0.7387	0.0153	0.7540	0.50 = 0.9953 "	0.9000
0.7387	0.0153	0.7540	0.60 = 1.1944 "	0.9180
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	0.70 = 1.3935 "	0.9240
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	0.80 = 1.5924 "	0.9320
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	0.90 = 1.7916 "	0.9400
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	1.00 = 1.9905 "	0.9480
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	1.35 = 2.6874 "	0.9720
0.7370	0.0206	0.7576	2.00 = 3.9810 "	0.9880
0.7376	0.0199	0.7575	3.00 = 5.9718 "	0.9960
0.7376	0.0199	0.7575	4.00 = 7.9624 "	1.0040
0.7387	0.0221	0.7588	5.00 = 9.9530 "	1.0000
0.7387	0.0221	0.7588	6.00 = 11.9440 "	1.0630
0.7374	0.0262	0.7636	7.00 = 13.9350 "	1.0680

Discussion of Results obtained in the First Series of Experiments.

It will be observed from the curve that when the alkali-strength is kept constant (about 6.64 equivalents), an increase in the amount of available oxygen in the oxide formed occurs with an increasing amount of ferri-

cyanide. The increase in the first four experiments is very rapid. After this there is a break or arrest in the curve corresponding with the composition, Co_3O_4 (oxygen equivalent = 0.66). Then the available oxygen increases rapidly to a point slightly below the composition of Co_2O_3 and subsequently slowly to Co_2O_3 . Here it remains practically constant at about 1.06 equivalent of available oxygen even with further increase in the amount of ferricyanide added. The final product obtained is therefore practically pure Co_2O_3 , slightly peroxidized. From the nature of the curve it is apparent that no direct peroxidation of cobalt occurs under these conditions. The cobaltous oxide is first oxidized to Co_3O_4 and then to Co_2O_3 ; six to eight equivalents of ferricyanide were actually required to carry the oxidation to Co_2O_3 even in the presence of an excess of alkali. Theoretically, one equivalent of ferricyanide with one equivalent of alkali can carry the oxidation to Co_2O_3 and two equivalents of ferricyanide with two equivalents of alkali are sufficient for oxidation to the CoO_2 stage. The results, therefore, indicate that the reaction does not proceed to completion in the sense of the following equation:—

In fact, the maximum degree of oxidation experimentally realized even with a very large excess like fourteen equivalents of ferricyanide was only slightly above Co_2O_3 (1.065 equivalents of available oxygen). It shows that as the degree of oxidation increases, the system tends to oppose further oxidation. This could not be due to any coating of a higher oxide over the next lower one thus preventing further oxidation, as the mixture in every case was thoroughly stirred with a mechanical stirrer for a definite period. On the other hand oxidation to Co_3O_4 becomes complete with a requisite

Equivalents of alkali.
Fig. II.

theoretical amount of ferricyanide (=0.67 equivalent), according to the equation:—

The second series of experiments (Table II, Fig. II) was performed in the same manner as the first: the amount of potassium ferricyanide (3.6 equivalents) was kept constant, while the amount of alkali was gradually increased.

TABLE II.
Cobalt taken = 0.09 gm.

KOH		K ₂ CO ₃ in grams.	Total alkali in grams.	Potassium ferricyanide		EQUIVALENTS OF AVAILABLE OXYGEN.
in grams	in equivalents.*			in grams	in equivalents.	
0.3009	1.515	0.0087	0.3096	1.8	3.6	0.7090
0.4005	2.679	0.0116	0.4121	"	"	0.8920
0.5000	3.841	0.0146	0.5746	"	"	0.9400
0.5996	5.005	0.0168	0.6164	"	"	0.9480
0.6992	6.168	0.0194	0.7188	"	"	0.9640
0.7545	6.814	0.0219	0.7764	"	"	0.9720
0.8983	9.494	0.0260	0.9243	"	"	0.9880
0.9978	9.656	0.0290	1.0269	"	"	0.9960
1.0974	10.820	0.0319	1.1293	"	"	1.0040
1.1970	11.984	0.0348	1.2318	"	"	1.0120
1.7960	18.981	0.0520	1.8480	"	"	1.0480
2.0007	21.375	0.0541	2.0548	"	"	1.0520
2.5037	27.249	0.0676	2.5713	"	"	1.1630
3.0023	33.074	0.0811	3.0834	"	"	1.1870
3.9900	44.612	0.1414	4.1304	"	"	1.2110
4.9875	56.791	0.1755	5.1630	"	"	1.2210

* Equivalents of alkali have been calculated by subtracting 0.1712 gm. in each case, for this amount of alkali was required to precipitate the cobalt as $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ from the solution and so played no part in the oxidation of the cobaltous hydroxide.

Discussion of Results Obtained in the Second Series of Experiments.

Here rapid oxidation occurs up to a point slightly below the composition of Co_2O_3 , then the rate slows down but as far as it has been investigated the oxidation proceeds continually through Co_2O_3 to a peroxidized state corresponding with 1.22 equivalents of available oxygen. As in the previous series, no direct peroxidation occurs. It can therefore be concluded that in the presence of an excess of alkali the extent of oxidation is increased, other conditions remaining unaltered. Peroxidation becomes prominent in this case only with 3.6 equivalents of ferricyanide. Oxidation to the Co_3O_3 stage with this amount of ferricyanide is effected with about eleven equivalents of alkali.

In Fig. II, as in Fig. I, a bend occurs at about 0.9 equivalents of available oxygen, that is a little below the composition of Co_2O_3 . Then the degree of oxidation increases steadily but at a much slower rate to beyond the Co_3O_3 stage. Hence it is apparent that the preparation of pure Co_2O_3 in presence of a very large excess of alkali by the addition of ferricyanide would be very difficult. The product in that case would probably consist of a mixture of Co_2O_3 with either a still higher oxide like CoO_2 or a lower oxide like Co_3O_4 . Here also as in the first series the oxidation is never quantitative. Excess of alkali, however, raises the oxidizing potential or capacity of ferricyanides to a certain extent. Two series of experiments in which the reaction was allowed to proceed to completion were then performed to ascertain the influence of the concentration of the reacting substances upon the results obtained. The results (Table III) show that the concentrations of the reacting substances have no influence on the results obtained.

TABLE III.

Cobalt taken = 0.09 gm.

	KOH.	K ₂ CO ₃ .	Total alkali.	K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆ .	Volume.	Equivalents of available oxygen.
First Series.	0.9978 g.	0.0290 g.	1.0268 g.	1.8 g.	125 to 500 c.c.	0.906
Second Series.	1.1895 g.	0.0322 g.	1.2217 g.	"	125 c.c.	1.012
	"	"	"	"	250 "	1.013
	"	"	"	"	500 "	1.008

The influence of temperatures below that of the decomposition of alkaline potassium ferricyanide solution upon the final results was then studied. The reacting solutions were brought to the required temperature before mixing. Then they were mixed and the reaction was allowed to proceed to completion at the same temperature (thermostat). The results (Table IV) show that temperature has no influence on the final results obtained, provided it is not very near that of the decomposition of potassium ferricyanide solution.

TABLE IV.

Cobalt taken = 0.081 gm.; alkali = 0.67 gm.;

 K₃Fe(CN)₆ = 6.3 gm.

Temperature °C.	Available oxygen calculated from the results in Table I.	Available oxygen found.
0° - 42°	0.1098 gm.	0.11 gm.

The following results (Table V) show that the degree of oxidation as determined by the estimation of ferrocyanide in the filtrate is very little affected by the time of contact of the precipitated oxide with the solution. In these experiments no time was allowed for stirring the mixed solution. Corresponding results obtained with stirring are also placed side by side for comparison.

TABLE V.

Cobalt taken = 0.09 gm.

KOH.	K ₂ CO ₃ .	Total alkali.	Ferrioyanide.	Available oxygen without stirring.	Available oxygen with stirring.
2.0007 g.	0.0541 g.	2.0548 g.	1.8 g.	0.0127 g.	0.0126; 0.0128
2.5087	0.0676	2.5713	1.8 g.	0.0143	0.0142
3.0023	0.0811	3.0834	1.8 g.	0.0145	0.0144; 0.0145

It has already been indicated in Table II that slight peroxidation occurs above a certain concentration of alkali when the amount of ferricyanide remains constant. The above experiments in Table V correspond with the conditions which give rise to the formation of this peroxidized product. Hence these results show that the reagent is not affected catalytically to any appreciable extent by the decomposition of the peroxide formed, though the latter may undergo some decomposition by long stirring or keeping as indicated by the results recorded in Table VI.

In a set of experiments the results of which are recorded in Table VI both the filtrate and the precipitated

oxide were analysed. It will be observed that in the first three experiments the available oxygen found in the precipitate is less than that calculated from the filtrate. The oxide CoO_2 is decomposed by water and the low value of oxygen in the precipitate was possibly due to the decomposition of the peroxide by the washing necessary to free it from ferricyanide; when no peroxidation can possibly occur, the two values agree closely (*vide* Table VI, Expt. 4).

TABLE VI.

Cobalt taken = 0.09 gm.

KOH.	K_2CO_3 .	Total alkali.	Ferricyanide.	Equivalent of available oxygen	
				from the filtrate.	in the precipitate.
2.0007 g.	0.0641 g.	2.0548 g.	1.8 g.	1.049	0.95
2.5027 ,,	0.0676	2.5713	,,	1.164	1.061
3.0023	0.0811	3.0834	,,	1.18	1.083
0.0387	0.0153	0.7540	0.39	0.795	0.788

The presence of nickel salts beyond a certain concentration and iron salts in general give low results and retard the oxidation of cobalt even when the amount of alkali is sufficient for the oxidation of cobalt to the Co_2O_3 stage allowing for what is required for the precipitation of nickel and iron as their hydroxides. This is evident from Tables VII, VIII and IX.

TABLE VII.

Cobalt taken.	Nickel added.	Available oxygen found.	Available oxygen without nickel.
0.096 g.	0.0186 g.	0.01327 g.	0.0130 g.
..	0.0273	0.0130	..
..	0.0409	0.0129	..
..	0.0682	0.0124	..
..	0.0954	0.0108	..

TABLE VIII.

Cobalt taken.	Iron added.	Available oxygen found.	Available oxygen without iron.
0.948 g.	0.0045 g.	0.0064 g.	0.0065 g.
..	0.0111	0.0063	..
..	0.0222	0.0052	..
..	0.0333	0.0047	..

TABLE IX.

Cobalt taken.	Iron added.	Alkali.	Ferrieyanide.	Available oxygen found.	Available oxygen without iron.
0.048 g.	0.0222 g.	0.8930 g.	7.2 g.	0.0054 g.	0.0066 g.
..	..	1.1203	8.9	0.0060	..
..	..	1.3475	10.8	0.0068	..
..	..	1.5668	12.0	0.0064	..

From the last table it will be observed that in presence of iron a very large excess of the reagent mixture is necessary to oxidize the cobalt to Co_2O_3 stage.

An attempt was also made to study the constitution of higher oxides of nickel by oxidation with alkaline ferricyanide. Two higher oxides, Ni_2O_3 and NiO_2 have been described by earlier workers. Howell (*loc. cit.*) has definitely established that by oxidation with alkaline hypochlorite solution the two oxides NiO_2 and Ni_2O_3 are formed simultaneously, that the former is unstable and decomposes readily to NiO , and that the sesquioxide is not oxidized directly to the peroxide.

The oxidation of nickel by alkaline ferricyanide was studied in exactly the same manner as in the case of cobalt; chemically pure nickel free from cobalt was employed. Tables X and XI indicate the results obtained.

TABLE X.

Nickel used = 0.046 gm.

KOH	K_2CO_3	Total alkali.	$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	Equivalents of available oxygen.
0.6235 g.	0.0100 g.	0.6335 g.	0.14 g.	0.0129
"	"	"	0.28 "	0.0172
"	"	"	0.84 "	0.0215
"	"	"	1.54 "	0.0258
"	"	"	2.38 "	0.0387
"	"	"	3.38 "	0.0430
"	"	"	4.62 "	0.0473
"	"	"	6.16 "	0.0645
"	"	"	7.14 "	0.0730

TABLE XI.

Nickel used = 0.0846 gm.

KOH.	K ₂ CO ₃	Total alkali.	K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	Equivalents of available oxygen.
0.7521 g.	0.0121 g.	0.0642 g.	1.7 g.	0.0300
1.2663 "	0.0203	1.2366	"	0.0344
1.9091 "	0.0306	1.9397	"	0.0430
3.1947 "	0.0512	3.2459	"	0.0730
4.4803	0.0718	4.5521	"	0.0817

Equivalents of available oxygen have been calculated on the basis of nickel used; unit equivalent being the stoichiometric amount necessary for the conversion of all the NiO to the sesquioxide Ni₂O₃.

From the above data it becomes apparent that with a constant amount of alkali, the amount of available oxygen increases very slowly with the increasing amount of ferricyanide, though the actual amount is very low. Similarly, with a constant quantity of ferricyanide, increasing the quantity of alkali raises the available oxygen-content of the precipitate. Here also the actual amount of increase in the available oxygen-content is very small, though the rate of increase is somewhat more rapid than in the previous case. With a very large constant excess of potassium ferricyanide the extent of oxidation increased at a greater rate than is indicated in Table XI, but in all these cases the extent of oxidation was very small.

It can therefore be concluded that nickel is much less easily oxidizable than cobalt. In other words, for the same equivalent amounts of nickel and cobalt, a greater concentration of a given oxidizing agent is

required for nickel. The concentration of alkaline ferricyanide which oxidizes cobalt to the sesquioxide Co_2O_3 , fails to form a higher oxide of nickel.

Summary.

(1). Alkaline ferricyanide under certain conditions can oxidize cobaltous hydroxide readily and quantitatively to Co_3O_4 . Rapid oxidation proceeds up to a little below Co_2O_3 , then further oxidation progresses extremely slowly. The oxidation of cobaltous hydroxide is gradual and progressive. No direct peroxidation or simultaneous formation of two higher oxides from $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ has been detected. The formation of two definite oxides Co_3O_4 and Co_2O_3 has been established and that of a peroxide, CoO_2 indicated.

(2). Other factors remaining unchanged, alkali increases the extent or degree of oxidation. With very large excess of alkali appreciable peroxidation occurs.

(3). Under certain conditions, with a limited amount of alkali and excess of ferricyanide, practically pure Co_2O_3 can be obtained.

(4). Temperatures up to 42°C and variation of the concentrations of the reacting solutions have no effect upon the character of the product obtained.

(5). The time of contact of the precipitate with the oxidizing solution has no effect upon the nature of the final product up to the Co_2O_3 stage. Peroxidized cobalt loses a part of its oxygen as shown in Table VI, but the alkaline ferro- or ferri-cyanide is not affected in any way thereby (Table V).

(6). The presence of nickel salts beyond a certain concentration and iron salts in general appears to retard the oxidation of cobalt.

(7). Even with a large excess of alkali and ferri-cyanide only a very small fraction of nickel is oxidized.

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